

Communication Driven Polyculturality of Modern TV Journalism: Polylingual Focus for Future LSP Teachers

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ABSTRACT: The article considers a well-established approach for differentiation between scientific, formal (official business), journalistic, artistic, conversational, sacred (confessional), and oratorical functional styles in the contexts of polyculturality and polylingualism as significant backgrounds for teaching languages of specific purposes. It is stated that the determining criteria for all these functional styles are the sphere of social activity, type and established way of thinking, purpose, stylistic load of the units used to convey the meaning to the people. The effectiveness of journalism in the representation of mass communication across the geographies is manifested in the fact that its content is regularly found in the speech of the broadest segments of the population. However, modern linguistics encounters a number of unresolved issues of describing the polylingual mode of mass communication in expression of polyculturalism, which determines the relevance of this study. It is revealed that the communication driven polyculturality and polylingual effect of mass communication in modern journalism make one whole with the needs analysis and relevant terminology in instruction of Telejournalism as an LSP (language for specific purposes) in different languages. It is characterized how the panorama of communication driven polyculturality and polylingualism, as well as the 'journalism' concept affect media communication. It is determined which are the stylistic possibilities of journalism in structuring, presenting and perceiving mass information in different cultures and languages, by covering the communicative aspects driven by polyculturality and polylingualism in modern journalism. It is also described that relevant language units are seen as a means of forming a language and communicative standard in journalistic texts, which can be adopted by future LSP teachers in educational settings for language instruction and acquisition in relation to terminology of journalism in different languages across the world. In the end, it is concluded what may be underlying for journalistic language in different languages to constitute the polycultural communication driven framework rather than that of multiculturalism; and to be advanced further in polylingual classes by future LSP educators.

KEYWORDS: mass media, polyculturality, multiculturalism, polylingualism, telejournalism, LSP, future LSP teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The developed functional and stylistic system and stylistic delimitation in means of expression are some of the main characteristic features of modern national languages. A well-established approach allows for differentiation between scientific, formal (official business), journalistic, artistic, conversational, sacred (confessional), and oratorical functional styles. Thus, Yermolenko (1999) notes that for all these functional styles the determining criteria are the sphere of social activity, type of thinking, purpose, stylistic load of the units used [27, p. 10]. A similar approach is observed in the works by Kozhina and the relevantly associated stylistic school [22; 26].

For the purpose of this paper, the functional variety of language, following the representatives of different stylistic domestic and foreign schools, means the system of language units, ways to combine and use them, as determined by social needs. It is considered the journalistic style, and the sphere of mass media, in particular, to be the most dynamic and socially oriented today.

The dictionary *Journalism* provides a comprehensive definition of mass media (or media) as follows: 'the common name of any information organizations and institutions and any information products they produce' [29, p. 91]. Modern research in the field of media communication uses the terms media or mass media. However, Mykhailyn, author of the *Journalism* dictionary, reasonably notes that these definitions are criticized in one aspect. Mykhailyn underlines that the concept of 'means' does not fully convey the role and importance of journalism in a democratic society, and the understanding of the whole set of print and electronic publications, television and radio communication is reduced only to understanding of tools for modeling public views and values and the impact

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on their users [29]. Therefore, it is agreed the definition and explanations by the dictionary author are sound and preference to the term 'journalism' is substantiated this way.

The effectiveness of journalism in the representation of mass communication across the geographies is manifested in the fact that its content is regularly found in the speech of the broadest segments of the population. However, modern linguistics encounters a number of unresolved issues of describing the polylingual mode of mass communication, which determines the relevance of this study.

The purpose of the research is to reveal the communication driven polyculturality and polylingual effect of mass communication in modern journalism, which involves clarifying the following tasks:

- 1) To characterize the panorama of communication driven polyculturality and polylingualism, as well as the 'journalism' concept in the light of media communication,
- 2) To determine the stylistic possibilities of journalism in structuring, presenting and perceiving mass information in different cultures and languages,
- 3) To cover the communicative aspects driven by polyculturality and polylingualism in modern journalism,
- 4) To describe language units as a means of forming a language and communicative standard in journalistic texts, which can be adopted by future LSP teachers in educational settings for language instruction and acquisition in relation to terminology of journalism in different language across the world,
- 5) To conclude what may be underlying for journalistic language in different languages to constitute the polycultural communication driven framework rather than that of multiculturalism; and to be advanced further in polylingual classes by future LSP educators.

LSP as abbreviated means language for specific purpose in general, and English for Telejournalism / Portuguese for Telejournalism / Ukrainian for Telejournalism / German for Telejournalism / Spanish for Telejournalism, etc., in particular.

The object of the research is a journalistic product, which may embody into any form, for instance, news, stories, TV titles, texts by journalists (reporters, newsmakers) and so on, intended for mass communication and dissemination of information locally and globally.

The subject of the research relates to language units in a relevant language of the polylingual areas under the study, which create a communication driven polyculturality as a space of modern journalism. These are lexical units – lexemes, as well as phraseological units, language clichés, stamps as language patterns, etc.

METHODOLOGY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Methodology

The methods and techniques used in the research process were chosen in accordance with the goals and stages of the study carried out. The main of these are provided below:

- Analysis of scientific literature, used to describe the theoretical framework of the communication driven polyculturality (polyculturalism) as opposed to multiculturalism in the study of television journalism, especially focused on issues of polylingual communication in a variety of cultures and languages,
- Synthesis, used in general theoretical and applied aspects, looking at the best practices for the implementation of the academic findings for relevant language acquisition and instruction when it comes to teaching terminology of journalism as language for specific purpose,
- Descriptive method, applied for (i) integration of language units in the aspect of the research topic, especially with the material of the Ukrainian language, (ii) clarification of pragmatics of journalistic texts in the aspect of communication driven polyculturalism and polylingualism,
- Comparative / contrastive method, for the neologisms in the journalistic text as exemplified within the Ukrainian culture and language.

Literature review

The literature study displays two mainstreams. One links to the study of polyculturality and polyculturalism as a phenomenon in linguistics, education, and culture study, and is opposed to multiculturalism and multiculturalism, correspondingly. The other stresses out the results and findings in the study of journalism per se in the linguistic context of the research. It speaks of the distinct features and significance of telejournalism, implementation of polylingualism as based on communicative principles and mechanisms, expressive and stylistic assessment of long-existing phenomena, objects, and events, embodied into the functional classes of certain lexemes and stereotypical phrases, on the one hand. On the other, it underlines the advanced approaches to special purpose language instruction and acquisition for LSP classrooms, in which journalism arises with its term system in a respective language corpus and determines the limited scope of language use as a subject in the professional domain of specialized knowledge

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[4, p.120-121]. It is as well the focus of existing and/or future LSP teachers to follow the enriching language source in polycultural mass media for the journalism linguistic domain [5, p. 201].

Kruhlenko states that polycultural education as a term derives from its concept in modern education “in the context of the national pedagogical theory development”. The researcher interprets the concept of polycultural education by adopting “the four C” (name given by the authors of this paper) approaches:

- (i) Comparative – anti-discrimination educational philosophy,
- (ii) Communicative – referring to mastery in a language by growing skills and competencies of intercultural communication,
- (iii) Competence – performance of roles strengthened by the polycultural component, and
- (iv) Cultural – “recognition of diversity and equality of cultures” [11, p. 9-12].

However, the concept of polycultural education may be treated much broader. For instance, Kuchmenko (2017) underlines that polycultural education whatever might be discussed makes part of any education, the key criterion of which is culture as a mankind phenomenon. Moreover, the scholar states that it is a means to overcome any obstacle to self-awareness and awareness of ethnic, and national culture, to “awareness of shared interests by many peoples in their endeavor for peace and agreement, progressing via cultural development” [13, p. 240]. Polyculturality as a field of research is of interest to Rubtsova, Krylova, Smolskaia, and Odinskaya (2020) for formation of intercultural skills with the polycultural personality in general and a student, in particular. Further, the authors note that “the processes of forming a polycultural linguistic personality and teaching a foreign language are interconnected”, inasmuch “the efficiency of one being dependent on the other” [18, p. 809]. It is agreed that their research findings specify the significant components of the educational process that is culture-oriented in association with foreign languages. Thus, the main components refer to appropriate selection of educational content, which is based on sociocultural approaches and the principle of professional orientation; then, the interaction between the teacher (in our case future LSP teacher delivering classes on Telejournalism in polylingual environments) and the student, which is carried out on a dialogical basis “in the framework of cooperation and co-creation” [18, p. 813]; and in the end, the use of interactive teaching forms and methods, including discussions, role play, drama, presentations, internet and design technologies, etc. [18, p. 810-821]. Their suggested multilevel blended model may be treated feasible at the launch stage for teaching Journalism / Telejournalism terminology in LSP classes provided the thorough needs analysis has been made.

It should be noted that polyculturality in a foreign language classroom and an LSP classroom in different countries as part of the polyculturalistic trend differs from the multiculturalism. The ideas of multicultural education go back to social movements in the United States of America, for example, the 1960s – the Civil Rights Movement, the Feminist Movement, the People with Disabilities Rights Movement, etc. According to Polyankina (2011), “multicultural education challenges educators to develop their competencies of multiculturalism”, resting their ideas on Dhillon (2005) that “multiculturalism signifies the diversity of forms of life” and recognizes the value of different social and cultural lifestyles and networks [17, p. 283].

This research stresses out that the biggest difference between the multiculturalism and polyculturalism is in recognition of particularities and distinguishments in languages and cultures as opposed to language and culture tolerance. Where “multicultural education can ease tensions peculiar to multicultural society by teaching skills in cross-cultural communication, interpersonal relations, perspective taking, contextual analysis, understanding alternative points of view and frames of reference, etc.” [17, p. 283], polyculturalism looks at tolerance and acceptance of different languages and cultures, sharing the common and enjoying respect. LSP students in polylingual classrooms with the help of LSP teachers may easily learn to share their viewpoints from different cultures and learn to accept the variety and if necessary adopt some other cultural customs, traditions, forms of lingual and extralingual expressions [6; 7].

Navalna (2011) in her monograph *Dynamics of the lexicon of Ukrainian periodicals as of the beginning of the XXI century* provides with a complex study of lexical diffuseness in the language of Ukrainian periodicals in the first decade of the 21st century. Navalna, in particular, analyses the stylistic use of vocabulary belonging to different styles. The paper identifies the intra- and extralinguistic factors in the stylistic processes and covers the significant expansion of the functional and stylistic spheres of lexical Ukrainian media particularly that of economics, which is also associated with our research in terms of LSP study [15]. The mentioned study demonstrates a trend to colloquialization and increase in such expressions of such language, identifies the functional and semantic manifestations of lexis in the new spheres of existence, and determines the stylistic potential of slang elements, which closely links to the hypotheses (research questions) under the paper. Zdroveha (2008) studies the theory and methods of journalistic creativity and defines journalism as a dynamic and complex process. The reason for that is undergoing constant change. According to the author, journalism is multifaceted both in terms of the different information flows discussed and different types of communication [28, p. 16]. Livshits emphasizes at the same time the role of television in the information society, by assessing freedom of access to information and cultural values accumulated by humanity, freedom of expression and, as a result, the free flow of ideas, which represent the basic values of a democratic society. All these are associated with network media, the Internet, and other infocommunications, and television is not mentioned in these projects even in connection with the problem of a

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single information space. In this regard, the design and identification of the features of the development of television in the information society are of particular relevance, and an effective mechanism for its construction is the implementation of the public media sphere model [14]. Next, it is important that the audience becomes an active social concept of multilateral television communication, acquires the features of one of the functional elements in the political governance. The transition of the passive viewer to the position of an active participant in the communication process puts the state and society in front of the need to develop new forms of organization and management of broadcasting systems, since the prospects for digital broadcasting open up new problems in the creation and functioning of socially oriented broadcasters [14].

Following the stated, it appears that among the institutional changes, the need for which is discussed above, is the transformation of television into a truly universal institution of public life in the information society, which will make it possible to turn the society of passive TV viewers into the main participant in socio-political discourses. This is where television and Internet may collaborate, however, it should be minded that television of convergent communication forms, by definition, presupposes the transition of a passive viewer into an active user who forms their tele-needs, into an equal participant in communication. The forms of modern digitization may facilitate the necessary processes and ways of multicultural and polycultural communication driven needs of the society may become global for polylinguistic trends in communication as well [5, p. 200-201].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The modern technocratic epoch is characterized by constant search, activation and improvement of mass media in all the cultures, changes in the direction and regulation of various modes of journalism in various languages as the formed branch of professional communication.

It is understood that journalism, according to the definition provided in Journalism, the dictionary and reference book authored and edited by Mykhailyn, stands for the below:

- 1) A social institution established to provide comprehensive and objective information to the subjects of public life about social reality,
- 2) A form of public and literary activity for collecting, processing and disseminating information through mass communication channels,
- 3) Periodicals in general, and recently all the media, including live, streaming, and electronic,
- 4) A scientific discipline that studies a wide variety of problems associated with this specialty,
- 5) Profession of creative media worker [29, p. 70–71].

It is seen that all the content in the main definition as studied contains a number of concepts and semes, which altogether define journalism as the fourth power.

For a long period of its development, journalism has been an elitist sphere of human communication – both from the standpoint of producing information (author a journalist) and from the standpoint of mass media consumption (recipient who a reader / listener). The methodological significance of polylingual manifestations in the process of mass communication in polycultures is determined by the fact that the practical implementation of polylingualism is based on communicative principles and mechanisms [6, p. 116-118].

Both in everyday speech and in the field of journalism is a large number of linguistic facts, which indicate either new realities or provide expressive and stylistic assessment of long-existing phenomena, objects, events, and so on. These include the following functional classes:

- 1) Lexemes – neologisms, occasionalisms, oxymorons in various languages,
- 2) Stereotypical phrases – proverbs, sayings, set phrases and collocations, journalistic stamps, language clichés, etc.

Firstly, generally speaking, the outlined units of the language system are relevant in the use of modern polycultural infotainment. It is found that they are the ones that set the latest communication modes in journalism. The constant use of such units contributes to changes in the language system, because over time their constant use translates into the plane of everyday things – both in terms of journalistic communication, and in terms of perception and use in their own speech by readers and users of media information. In addition, the active dissemination of expressive language in the field of mass communication contributes to the deepening of polylingual issues of understanding the dynamics of modern media: the correlation of the degree of polylingualism of the journalist and the user of journalism. Moreover, in learning or teaching terminology of journalism as a language of specific purpose it is relevant to pay attention to this fact on top to the needs analysis by the LSP teachers in a polylingual classroom.

It is revealed that aspect analysis of the theoretical basis of the study summarizes one of the most studied sections of modern linguistics. For media people, new words and clichéd expressions are special units that form content that is perceived by viewers, readers and listeners. Perfection and manner of writing, use of language components affect the success of a message.

It is found that particularly popular in the language of the media are new words that are just beginning to be widely used or are gaining a certain frequency, breaking away from some professional narrow field or occasional use. Neologisms are one of the sources of enrichment with the language of television, its constant updating. The appearance of neologisms in the vocabulary of

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journalists is a constant process that is under the close attention of scientists. This is due to the fact that journalists react quickly to changes in life, as well as directly to the emergence of new concepts that are actively used in language.

The active appearance of neologisms in the Ukrainian and Russian, Spanish and Portuguese, German and Dutch languages, and their spread became the prerequisites for the creation of a classification of neoplasms. Analyzing the article by Bayrachna about the role of neologisms in language development, it is noted that the main two groups of new vocabulary are mainly distinguished:

- Common language innovations, and
- Individual-authorial [3, p. 90].

Thus, the group of colloquial neologisms consists of actual lexical components, or those that replace the classical, typical concepts with the intention to update and neologize them. An important factor is that they are common among native speakers and perform a nominative function.

It is revealed that the determinant that catalyzed the process of formation of current neologisms is the development that determines the name in society from almost all spheres of human life. The emergence of these concepts is demonstrated in the intention to name objects and phenomena that (a) appear or (b) have long been known and reinterpreted from the standpoint of bilingualism / trilingualism / polylingualism:

- (a) From English: *europanness, meme, blockchain, chip*;
- (b) From English: *guide, speechwriter, monster, default*, etc.

These examples brightly demonstrate a need in communication driven polyculturality among different nations and lay people. Not so long ago, they were used to be heard within professional groups of people that share specialised knowledge in some professional domain, which language is peculiar and known to that very limited group of people [4].

Next, individual-authorial innovations are words created by the authors of materials and used in a specific text. According to Hladka, in addition to what they call concepts, they also perform an emotionally expressive function, i.e. play a role in ensuring the imagery of the material [9, p. 32]. For example,

UA *Друга ракетка України здобула волюву перемогу над американкою на турнірі в Римі (Druha raketka Ukrayiny здобула vol'ovu peremohu nad amerykankoyu na turniri v Rymi) / literary EN **Ukraine's second racket** won a strong-willed victory over the American at the tournament in Rome* [Source: TSN, 1 + 1 – Ukrainian news TV-channels, 16 September 2020], or

UA *Танцюючі носії трун відпочивають: дівчина станцювала тверк на гробі і стала новим мемом (Tantsyuyuchi nosiyi trun vidpochyvayut': divchyna stantsyuvala tverk na hrobi i stala novym memom) / literary EN (lit. EN) *The dancing coffin-carriers are having a rest (are falling far behind): the girl danced on the coffin and became a new meme** [Source: UNIAN, 17 September 2020].

Modern infotainment numbers around tens of thousands of neologisms distributed through journalism. Therefore, the neolingual complex can be divided into two groups:

- Those lexemes that are active units of living speech, and
- Single word forms that are not used in the communication of native speakers, but convey language curiosities.

As analyzed, the broadcast of some modern TV channels demonstrates active accumulation of all the important phenomena with modern demos, which arrives that the media product is filled with neologisms.

It was decided to consider the vocabulary of popular authors who use much mass media in their journalism and next, it was selected and shortlisted that a number of neologism groups are more frequently used than the others (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1 Thematic groups by the most frequently used neologisms

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The result is thematic groups of such neologisms together with their selected Ukrainian equivalents known to have entered the general circulation.

Internet & social media: for example, the currently popular word *ban*:

UA *Його сторінку в Інтернет-мережі не раз банили* (Yoho storinku v Internet-merezhi ne raz banyly) / lit. EN *His page on the Internet has been banned more than once* [Source: News, Channel 24 – Ukrainian news TV-channels, 31 August 2020].

The Ukrainian equivalent of this word is UA *заборона* (zaborona) ‘a ban’ or UA *обмеження* (obmezhennia) ‘a restriction’. However, the native Ukrainian word is hardly ever used if at all. Instead, it is transliterated into Latin and used across the media, mainly for Internet users.

Similarly, in modern TV news the word *hashtag* is often used as transliteration of the English lexeme rather than its local language equivalent:

UA ... *відповідний хештег запущено в соцмережах* (vidpovidnyy kheshteh zapushcheno v sotsmerezhakh) / lit. EN ... *the corresponding hashtag has been launched in social networks* [Source: TSN, Channel 1 + 1, 21 September 2020].

That said viewers understand the word, which is preceded by a “#” symbol after which one can find user posts in the social network on the topic.

Fashion: in television programs, especially those related to culture and fashion, it is often possible to hear neologisms generated by development. For example, UA *тренч* (trench) ‘a trench coat’:

UA *Весна додасть до нашого гардеробу тренчі* (Vesna dodast' do nashoho harderobu trenchi) / lit. EN *Spring will add trench coats to our wardrobe* (TV channel 24).

It is from a story about the fashion collection by Oksana Karavanska, the famous Ukrainian designer. Using this and similar innovations, journalists inform viewers about new models of raincoats that went on sale in the spring.

Politics: in the language of mass media, irrespective of a language – Ukrainian, Russian, Polish, German, French, Spanish, Portuguese, etc., lexemes are actively used to denote neo-processes related to state formation, for instance. Their number is growing higher and higher [29, p. 77], for example:

UA *Політичний тиск на Україну, – «слухи» про заяву Росії щодо неможливості проведення «Норманді»* (Politychnyy tysk na Ukrayinu, – «sluhu» pro zayavu Rosiyi shchodo nemozhlyvosti provedennya «Normandi») / *Political pressure on Ukraine – “servants” comments on Russia’s statement of the impossibility to hold “Normandy”* [Source: News, Channel 24, 18 September 2020], or

UA *Політичне Ватерлоо: цікаві факти про запеклу боротьбу скандальних мерів на місцевих виборах* (Politychne Waterloo: tsikavi fakty pro zapeklu borot'bu skandal'nykh meriv na mistsevykh vyborakh) / lit. EN *Political Waterloo: interesting facts about the fierce struggle of scandalous mayors in local elections* [Source: TSN, Channel 1 + 1, 18 September 2020].

In this context, TV journalists actively use the phrases of UA *політичний тиск* (politychnyy tysk) ‘political pressure’ and UA *політичне Ватерлоо* ‘political Waterloo’. It is considered that these can be seen as typical phrases that are (a) innovations, the basis for which was borne by the word *politics*, which deepened the semantic characteristics, and/or as (b) modified phraseologisms used to denote a certain action or event.

- (a) Innovations: UA *політична більшість* ‘political majority’, UA *політичні дії* ‘political action’, UA *політичні баталії* ‘political battles’, UA *політичні чинники* ‘political factors’, etc.,
- (b) Modified phraseologisms.

Economy and economics: in order to denote new economic concepts in infotainment relevant neologisms as transliterated rather than translated are found, which creates a certain shared polycultural and polylingual fields, in particular:

- 1) Economic concepts, cf: UA *макророекономіка* (makroekonomika) and EN *macroeconomics*, UA *євроекономіка* (yevroekonomika) and EN *euroeconomics*, UA *геоекономіка* (heoekonomika) and EN *geoeconomics*, UA *неоекономіка* (neoeekonomika) and EN *neoeconomics*;
- 2) Names of persons by type of activity: UA *бізнесмен* (biznesmen) and EN *businessman*, UA *бізнесовець* (biznesovets) and EN *businessman*, UA *маркетолог* (marketoloh) and EN *marketer*, UA *рекламодавець* (reklamodavets) and EN *advertiser*, UA *менеджер* (menedzher) and EN *manager*;
- 3) Names of monetary units: UA *євро* (yevro) and EN *euro*, UA *криптовалюта* (kryptovalyuta) and EN *cryptocurrency*, UA *биткойн* (bytkojn) and EN *bitcoin*, UA *електронний поліс* (elektronnyu polis) and EN *electronic policy*, UA *віртуальна монета* (virtualna moneta) and EN *virtual coin*, UA *віртуальна грошова платформа* (virtualna hroshova platforma) and EN *virtual monetary platform*.

In our opinion, it is worth giving a whole list of cryptocurrencies used by journalists in different languages and used in their English transliteration - not only to cover financial and economic issues, but also to show the social status of a person: *Bitcoin, Ethereum, Litecoin, Bitcoin Cash, Monero, Dash, Zcash, VertCoin, BitShares, Factom, NEM (XEM), Dogecoin, MaidSafeCoin, DigiByte, Nautiluscoin, Clams* and others [Cryptocurrency]. It is found all the same across different cultures and languages, which

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definitely speaks of polyculturality in Journalism as a language for specific purpose, as well as of the relevant polylingualism inasmuch all the mentioned terms are found in the European and other continental languages.

It is also found that most of the new vocabulary used has an international character, and therefore it is assumed such new lexis in the languages enjoys its universality in the process of spreading communication flows and, consequently, consumer perception of information in the global journalism. In understanding the two-way process and components of communication, the theory of semantic universals by Vezhbytska is addressed, that underlines that the communication of universal words for most recipients should represent the “universal alphabet of human thought” [25].

However, the language of journalism has national and cultural components that reflect the internal socio-political and socio-cultural situation in the country. It is agreed with Polonskiy on the cognitive objectification of the concept of “communicative situation”, which, in addition to universality in the structuring and categorization of communicative space, outlines the features of its national representation and emphasizes that “the frame of “communicative situation” also has ethnocultural labeling. The result of language awareness, as it is known, always has an artefact character” [16, p. 160].

Therefore, recently it has been traced in Ukrainian for Journalism the ways of how the words UA *національний* (natsionalnyy) / EN *national*, UA *державний* (derzhavnyy) / EN *state* expressed by the adjective, UA *державницький* (derzhavnytskyy) / EN *statehood* (used as preposition to the head noun in the compound noun phrase) have become more engaged and frequently used. These days, the latter lexeme has acquired in the language of the media a new shade to denote the name of the highest manifestation in the symbiosis of concepts by the formula: nationalism + statehood, for example: UA *державницькі сили* (derzhavnytski syly) / EN *state forces*, UA *позиції* (pozytsiyi) / EN *positions*, UA *функції* (funktsiyi) / EN *functions*.

Lexemes that denote new social realities are filled with expressive national and cultural meaning. The modern language policy of Ukrainian TV channels is also marked by the intensification of many word-formation models, according to which a large group of socio-political vocabulary is formed. Basic word formation and abbreviation are among the most productive ways to create new words used in journalistic practice. For example, often in the news or live broadcasts with the participation of experts and political scientists, the following lexemes are used and many other innovations are updated: UA *псевдополітик* (psevdropolityk) / EN *pseudo-politician*, UA *екополітика* (ekopolityka) / EN *eco-politics*, UA *кучмократія* (kuchmokratia) / EN *kuchmocracy* – from the name of Ukraine’s President Leonid Kuchma, UA *домооренда* (domoorenda) / EN *household lease*.

Another group of neologisms in Ukrainian for Journalism and Ukrainian for Telejournalism are words formed with the prefix *супер-* (EN *super-*):

UA *суперзірка* (superzirka) / EN *superstar*,
UA *супердіва* (superdiva) / EN *superwoman*,
UA *супердержава* (superderzhava) / EN *superstate*,
UA *суперполітик* (superpolityk) / EN *super-politician*,
UA *супердипломат* (superdyplommat) / EN *superdiplomat*,
UA *суперзброя* (superzbroya) / EN *superweapon*,
UA *суперсучасний* (supersuchasnyy) / EN *supermodern*,
UA *супервигідний* (supervyhidnyy) / EN *superbeneficial*,
UA *супероригінальний* (superoryhinalnyy) / EN *superoriginal*, etc.,

Although the use of such words is not always justified. Today, in Ukrainian / Russian for [Tele] Journalism lexical items with the forming root of *Europe* have become very popular, for example:

UA *Євросоюз* (Yevrosoyuz) / EN *European Union*,
UA *європарламент* (yevroparlament) / EN *Europarlament, European Parliament*,
UA *євроатлантичний* (yevroatlantychnyy) / EN *Euro-Atlantic*,
UA *євроазійський* (yevroaziyskyy) / EN *Eurasian*,
UA *євроінтеграція* (yevrointehratsiya) / EN *European integration*,
UA *євровіза* (yevrovisa) / EN *Eurovisa*,
UA *євробанк* (yevrobank) / EN *Eurobank*,
UA *євровалюта* (yevrovaliuta) / EN *Eurocurrency*,
UA *євробанкнота* (yevrobanknota) / EN *Eurobanknote*,
UA *євроваучер* (yevrovaucher) / EN *Eurovoucher*,
UA *євроремонт* (yevroremont) / EN *Eurorepair*, etc.

Further, it is traced how in journalistic texts, depending on their genre, the authors of publications partly use marginal vocabulary, which includes youth slang, thus demonstrating a tribute to a certain age category of readers (adolescent or youth). However, sometimes the limit is very shaky in such language creation that the elite consumer (and not only the mass) is perceived as a reflection of the spontaneous development of journalistic creativity and standard. Therefore, a whole group of slang vocabulary dominates the mass media language, for example:

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UA *башика, думалка* (bashka, dumalka) – EN head,

UA *забити* (zabyty) – EN ignore something, neglect,

UA *вписка* (vpyska), lit. EN entry (acceptance) party – EN a party with many hard drinks,

UA *голівудити* (holivudyty) ‘to hollywood’ – EN relax, have fun,

UA *хавати* (khavaty) – EN to eat, to have a good meal,

UA *хейтити* (heityty) ‘to hate’ – EN to humiliate, to openly mock,

UA *секситись* (seksytysia) ‘to have sex’ – EN to date someone or have an intercourse with a partner of different sex, etc.

Analyzing the texts of TVjournalists, it is noted that the slang vocabulary consists of at least two layers: these are words to denote the phenomena of reality that the speaker wants to distinguish, and lexemes by which the phenomenon can be hidden.

In the creation of slang vocabulary, it is found that various modifications that reflect the ironic expression with paronymic convergence. The metamorphosis of slang word formation is a metaphor or reinterpretation of words in the vernacular. Thus, the most figurative slang lexemes are formed in Ukrainian / Russian for Journalism:

UA *гелік* (helik) or *точила* (tochyla) ‘an expensive car similar to an UAZ’,

UA *тараканник* (tarakannyk) / lit. EN cockroaches’ house ‘a dormitory’, and

UA *флекс* (fleks) – EN to brag showing some peculiarities by bravado.

Slangisms are also formed via pun:

UA *махнач* (machnach) ‘a person who has thick and naughty hair’ (from the name of the revolutionary Nestor Makhno),

UA *агритись* (ahrytysia) – to feel irritated and angry, from English ‘angry’.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the efficiency of response to numerous social events, the combination of expressiveness and conciseness of media broadcasting determine the widespread use of clichés. Clichéd ready-made blocks (as in the examples above) not only save the efforts of the author of the media text to express current information, but also simplify the communication process itself. This feature of language clichés is fully consistent with the characteristics of the environment in which they live, in particular in light of the diffusion of new information.

Therefore, the processes of journalistic lexicon creation are easy to trace the development trends of society and its preferences. The journalist must feel the signs not only of the time in which the text was written, but also of the epoch in which it is spoken. This approach helps to understand the relevance of a particular vocabulary and, conversely, to see its inappropriateness in a particular text [27]. However, it can be assumed that such use of newly formed neologisms in journalistic speech is quite justified, if only because the Ukrainian equivalents are not so bright and concise for perception. However, linguists insist that authors should interpret such expressions in parentheses, as they may be unknown and incomprehensible to the general public.

In the end, the field of journalism is a branch of communicative activity, where, on the one hand, language units reflect the current response to current socio-political and social events, and on the other hand, the dynamics of media language and new trends in the representation of mass discourse are clearly visible. As necessary as the needs analysis for any LSP course, is it the focus by existing and future LSP teachers for communication driven polyculturality when it comes to the study and analysis of terminology with Ukrainian for [Tele-] Journalism, Polish for [Tele-] Journalism, and Spanish for [Tele-] Journalism, etc., in polylingual classes. Internationalisms and borrowings from the English language into business areas, politics, economy, fashion, and slang irrespective of the language significantly influence local languages, by soaking into the national lexical systems and, thus, creating the shared perception within different ethnic peoples. Polyculturality in this case demonstrates the shared vision of nations and cultures globally, perception, and modern trends in the society for innovations and changes. It is the tolerance to languages and cultures, which altogether causes no need in rejection. On the contrary, assimilation is becoming more and more expressed as opposed to multiculturalism and multiculturality, correspondingly.

Challenging as it may become soon, loss of individuality as an ethnos may be questioned, which would make another trajectory for further study.

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